
The Role and Importance of Accommodation Services in the Development of Tourism

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Abstract. *In the conditions of the market economy, it is important to study international experience and improve the quality of service by applying it to the development of the hotel industry in our country.*

Keywords: *hotels, service, guests, reception, apartment.*

INTRODUCTION

From the first days of independence in Uzbekistan, tourism services in the field of service provision have been interpreted as modern services, and attention to these services has risen to the level of state policy. Necessary organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of the industry have been created, and relevant regulatory documents have been adopted by the government. The fact that work in this direction is still ongoing is proof of our opinion. Today, it should be noted that the tourism sector is of great importance for the development of the economy of countries and regions, and that it is one of the priority sectors of the world economy of the 21st century.

Creating favorable economic and organizational and legal conditions for the rapid development of tourism as a strategic branch of the country's economy, more fully and effectively using the tourism potential of the regions, fundamentally improving the management of the tourism network, creating national tourism products and promoting them in world markets Prayer is one of the important factors in forming a positive image of Uzbekistan.

In the implementation of these tasks, on the basis of the Decree "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" announced on December 2, 2016 at the initiative of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, the Republic of Uzbekistan Tourism Development The establishment of the state committee raised the reforms in this field to a new level.

It should be noted that by the Decree, the target tasks and priorities of the state policy in the field of tourism were determined, and the specific functions of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan as an authorized state body in the field of tourism were determined.

As a logical continuation of the reforms, the head of state's visit to Samarkand on April 14 of this year, along with getting acquainted with the creative works and socio-economic reforms carried out in the region, paid special attention to the issues of using the huge tourist potential of the region.

It is known that tourism is one of the main directions of the economy of Samarkand region. In this regard, systematic work is being carried out in the region on the rational use of tourist resources, increasing the types of services provided and adapting their quality to modern requirements. Thanks to the opportunities and privileges created in our country, more than a hundred hotels and more than 80 tourist companies are operating in Samarkand today.

From year to year, their material and technical base is strengthened, and the possibilities of providing high-quality service at the level of modern requirements are expanding. In addition, new tourist routes are being opened in regional districts in order to develop ecological, health, agro and active types of tourism, to support domestic tourism.

Faster development of the tourism industry, increasing its share in the economy, and ensuring the quality of tourist services are also defined as one of the priority tasks in the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021".

In accordance with it, in the medium-term perspective, in order to develop the concept of development of the tourism industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the Program of concrete measures for the implementation of the Concept in 2017-2021 and to ensure the wide involvement of business entities in this field, "Tourism to The event for the development of a new version of the Law on

In its place, the favorable business environment created in the field of tourism increases the activity of many business entities in the field of tourism and leads to the offer of quality services by them. This, in turn, serves for many foreign tourists to come to our country, take advantage of the opportunities created, get acquainted with the hospitality traditions of our people, and take a cultural vacation.

The development of the tourism sector directly gives a great impetus to the development of the hotel industry. Today, hotel business is the most developed business in the world. The hotel business includes not only large hotels, but also small private hotels, because dealing with any kind of hotel business remains the most profitable business not only in the field of tourism, but also in the economy. According to the World Tourism Organization, in 1997, the total number of available rooms in hotels and other tourist accommodation facilities in the world was 29 million. Today, this indicator has increased several times. The type of activity we call tourism includes the hospitality industry and travel arrangements. The hotel business is not an industry that develops by itself, it certainly requires scientific approaches. Marketing is the most important activity in the hotel business. Successful marketing depends on organizing the entire travel experience. Tourism is the most important and profitable sector of the economy. This sector ranks 3rd in terms of providing employment to the population. 400 billion to tourists every year. dollar services are provided. The importance of marketing in the restaurant sector of this chain is increasing. This industry has attracted such food companies as Pizza Hut (Pepsico), Kentucky Fried Chicken (Pepsico), Olive Garden (General Mills). The hotel business has similar trends. 7 hotels in the USA - Holiday Inn, Sheraton, Marriott, Hilton, Hyatt, Ramada, Quality - earn more than a billion dollars a year. As the competition increases, hotels are more and more in need of their marketing managers. In most hotels, the position of marketing manager has the same responsibility as the general manager.

The modern development of the hotel industry has a unique appearance. Among the trends observed in the development of hospitality industry enterprises in recent years, the following can be included:

- deepening of specialization of hotel and restaurant services;
- establishment of international hotel and restaurant networks;
- development of the network of small enterprises;
- introduction of new computer technologies in the hospitality industry.

Enterprises may have different specializations. Hotels serve representatives of a certain segment of the tourist market, for example, customers who devote their working vacation to golf, skiing, horse riding, etc., participation in congresses, exhibitions, fairs, etc. can specialize in serving tourists.

The deepening of specialization of hospitality enterprises is also connected with the establishment of international networks. Such networks play a major role in the development and implementation of a high standard of service.

A network usually means a group of enterprises engaged in collective business and operating under the direct control of the network management. By the beginning of the 1990s, US hotel chains gained a leading position in the world. They displaced Travelodge International and Master Hosts International from Europe among the ten leading hotel chains in the world. If we look at the table, even among the twenty largest hotels in the world, the majority of hotels are located in the United States of America.

In this table, we can see twenty leading hotels of the world. The first of these is Messa Clock Tower with a total number of 8,000 rooms, the second is Gostinitisa Izmaylovo, with a total number of 7,500 rooms, and the third is First World Hotel, with a total number of 6,118 rooms.

Largest hotels in the world

№	Name of hotels	The total number of numbers	Countries where hotels are located
1	Messa S1osk Toweg	8000	Saudi Arabia
2	Gostinitisa Izmaylovo	7500	Moscow, Russia
3	First World Hotel	6118	Malaysia
4	MGM Grand	5690	Las Vegas
5	Ambassador City Jomtlen	4631	Thailand
6	Luxor	4408	Las Vegas
7	Mandalay Wow	4341	Las Vegas
8	The Venetian	4027	Las Vegas
9	Excalibur	4008	Las Vegas
10	Bellagio	3993	Las Vegas
11	Circus Circus	3774	Las Vegas
12	Fiamingo Las Vegas	3565	Las Vegas

13	Hilton Hawaiian Village	3386	Honolulu
14	Caesar's Palace	3349	Las Vegas
15	Mirage	3044	Las Vegas
16	Monte Carlo	3002	Las Vegas
17	Las Vegas Hilton	2956	Las Vegas
18	Paris	2916	Las Vegas
19	Treasure Island	2885	Las Vegas
20	Gaylord Opryland	2883	Nashville

By the mid-1990s, more than 30% of the global hotel stock was controlled by large hotel associations and chains. Like most other trends, the establishment of hotel chains was founded in the United States.

The International Association of Hotels divides hotel chains into three categories:

- corporate hotels - hotel corporations with a large number of enterprises;
- networks of independent enterprises united to use the common booking system, marketing, advertising concepts and other services that add value to a particular enterprise;
- Networks providing management services.

According to experts, in the 21st century, this is exactly what hotels without a restaurant (the restaurant is located next to the hotel) that provide services at comfortable, convenient, moderate prices, have all the conditions for work and rest, are hospitality. takes a leading place in the industry.

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